

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/383976214>

Localization of grazing cows using Yolov8 object detection and known landmarks

Conference Paper · September 2024

CITATION

1

READS

118

4 authors:

Jérémie Haumont

KU Leuven

5 PUBLICATIONS 6 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Pieter-Jan De Temmerman

Instituut voor Landbouw en Visserijonderzoek

34 PUBLICATIONS 1,348 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Jürgen Vangeyte

Instituut voor Landbouw en Visserijonderzoek

150 PUBLICATIONS 3,472 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Jarissa Maselyne

Instituut voor Landbouw en Visserijonderzoek

56 PUBLICATIONS 720 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Localization of grazing cows using Yolov8 object detection and known landmarks.

Authors: Jérémie Haumont¹, Pieter-Jan De Temmerman¹, Jürgen Vangeyte¹, Jarissa Maselyne¹
¹ *ILVO (Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food), Technology and Food Science Unit - Agricultural engineering, Burg. van Gansberghelaan 115 bus 1, 9820 Merelbeke, Belgium*

jeremie.haumont@ilvo.vlaanderen.be

Abstract

Ensuring adequate feed intake is a major challenge for farmers when adopting grazing in the management of dairy cows, despite the recognized welfare benefits of pasture access. This study aims to develop a vision-based system for localizing grazing cows in pastures as the rise of AI and edge computing offers great capabilities to assist in feed management.

A total of 3039 labeled images of cows on the pasture were used to train the YoloV8 model, with 62% for training, 26% for validation, and 12% for testing. The dataset was augmented by applying geometric transformations and variations in lighting and contrast before the model was trained to achieve a model that is robust to varying light conditions and positions of the cow in the image.

Training Yolov8 nano, small, and medium models on this dataset yielded promising results. mAP50 values were consistently high (>0.87) across training, validation, and test sets for all model sizes. The nano version seems the best suited for applications in a pasture due to less computation power requirements than the other models. The image-based localization achieved an accuracy of $0.89 \pm 0.50m$ for cows in a pasture. A sensitivity analysis of the localization algorithm also indicated that camera-based localization of the cow in a pasture is sensitive to changes in the height of the detected cow, but advances in animal pose estimation might benefit the investigated localization approach. Future research should focus on independent datasets to validate the models and quantify overfitting and on incorporating behavior identification to achieve an integrated monitoring system.

Keywords: object detection, animal tracking, grazing, yolov8, dairy cows, outdoor localization

Introduction

In Europe, a trend towards zero-grazing for dairy cattle has been observed over the past decade (van den Pol-van Dasselaar et al., 2020). Nonetheless, grazing land still represents 25% of the utilized agricultural area (JRC, 2015). The choice of a farmer to adopt or abate grazing depends on multiple factors such as the climate and field conditions, the economic circumstances, but also the managerial situation, such as the size of the herd, use of a milking robot (van den Pol-van Dasselaar et al., 2020).

Providing pasture access for dairy cows provides several welfare and health benefits for cows (Arnott et al., 2017). This includes reduced risk for lameness, mastitis, and increased ability to express natural behavior. However, these benefits are dependent on the weather and pasture-specific conditions. For example, the path towards the pasture should be well-maintained to prevent lameness, in wet conditions the udder can remain dirty, resulting in an increased risk of

mastitis, and when not enough shading areas are provided, the animals can be exposed to thermal discomfort (Arnott et al., 2017; Aubé et al., 2022).

A recent survey amongst dairy farmers in Flanders indicated that one of the major reasons for choosing zero-grazing is the variation in grass supply due to weather variability, which will lead to production fluctuations (Cloet, 2022). Additionally, changes in grass supply and quality might lead to hunger and negatively impact the animals' welfare.

Technological innovations that contribute to improved feed management to prevent hunger in highly productive cows can alleviate this hurdle and increase the adoption of grazing. Accurate real-time localization and behavior classification are major challenges that should be tackled to advance precision livestock farming of pasture-based animals.

Today, there exist multiple localization technologies that are suitable for outdoor localization such as global navigation satellite system (GNSS), ultra-wideband (UWB), radio frequency identification (RFID), Bluetooth, or a low power wide area network (LoRaWAN). However, these technologies make a trade-off between accuracy, battery life, and range. For example, GNSS sensors have an accuracy of 3 to 5m across the globe but have limited battery life or very low measurement frequency and are limited to outdoor applications. On the other hand, UWB has high accuracy and consumes little energy but is challenging to use outdoors due to the requirements of many base stations. Additionally, these localization sensors also require additional sensors for behavior identification. However, with the rise of AI for computer vision and edge computing, camera systems offer great potential for monitoring pasture-based animals.

This study aimed to investigate the ability of camera systems for real-time localization of cows on the pasture with high accuracy.

Materials and methods

Imaging setup and data acquisition

The setup consisted of a 3 megapixel (MP) RGB camera (Daheng MER2-302-56U3C, Daheng Group, Beijing, China) with a 4mm focal length lens that was mounted on a pole at 5.5m high. The camera was connected over USB to a Nvidia Jetson Xavier AGX (Nvidia, Santa Clara, CA, USA). The camera setup collected videos at 30 frames per second (fps) at two distinct locations. At the first site, 15 lactating cows were monitored around the drinking bin. The animals were put on the pasture after milking (6 a.m.) in the morning and were brought back to the stable before milking in the evening (4 p.m.). On the second site, 9 dry cows were housed in a stable with free access to the pasture. At this site, the camera was positioned such that the whole pasture could be observed.

From all videos 3039 frames, equally separated in time across the movies, were extracted in which the cows were annotated by drawing a bounding box around each cow, resulting in 15 633 annotations. Using this dataset the YoloV8 object detection model was finetuned for detecting cows in the pastures (Jocher et al., 2023). In this study, the performance of the nano, small, and medium variations of the model was compared. To assess the models' performance the dataset was split into a training (62%), validation (26%), and test (12%) set, frames from a single movie were kept together in one of the three sets to prevent information leakage as much as possible. Before training, the dataset was augmented by applying geometric transformations and variations in lighting and contrast.

Localization algorithm

The acquired images only provide 2D information, so the GPS coordinates of the cows could not be directly determined from detections and require some image processing to extract the cows' position. Therefore, the images were transformed using a perspective transformation such that the transformed image provides a top view of the pasture (Figure 1). The transformation matrix was estimated based on the correspondence of 4 four locations in the image and their GPS coordinates retrieved from satellite images. When a cow is detected in the original image, its GPS coordinates can be determined by converting the bounding box to a cow reference point where the cow is standing on the pasture. The cow image coordinates of this point (x_c, y_c) were determined as:

$$x_c = x_1 + w/2 \quad (1)$$

$$y_c = y_1 + 0.9 * h \quad (2)$$

With x_1, y_1 , the pixel coordinates of the upper left corner of the bounding box, and h, w the height and width of the bounding box. Subsequently, the GPS coordinates of that point in the image are determined by multiplying it with the perspective transformation matrix.

Figure 1 Visualization of (a) the original image acquired with our setup of the pasture and (b) the transformed with the red lines indicating the borders of the pasture, the orange rectangle a bounding box around the detected cow, and the blue dot the image coordinates used for conversion to GPS coordinates. The black arrows in (a) indicate the image reference points on the image where GPS locations were collected and used to determine the perspective transform.

Accuracy assessment

In this study, the accuracy of the localization algorithm was determined by comparing the image-derived geolocations with GPS references. This was done using a plastic cow that was placed at 28 locations throughout our testing pasture (Figure 2a). At each location, the cow was placed and rotated in five different orientations relative to the camera. The plastic cow was 2m in length and 1.3m high, the GPS location was determined using an RTK GNSS antenna (Emlid reach RS2+, Emlid tech, Budapest, Hungary) which was placed on a fixed location on the back of the cow and has centimeter accuracy (Figure 2b). At each location and orientation, an image of the pasture was recorded and the bounding box of the cow was converted to its GPS coordinates using the localization algorithm.

Figure 2 (a) The positions in the pasture of the plastic cow indicated by blue dots and the position of the camera indicated by the blue cross. (b) A detailed image of the plastic cow with the fixed position of the RTK GPS for reference measurements indicated by a red cross.

Sensitivity analysis

This georeferencing approach for animals using 2D RGB cameras is influenced by several parameters such as (i) the image coordinates of each reference point (ii) their corresponding GPS coordinates, and (iii) the derived position of the cow based on the bounding box from the object detection. A Sobol sensitivity analysis was conducted to assess the influence of those parameters on the accuracy of the localization algorithm using the SALib python package (Herman & Usher, 2017). For this, the image coordinates (x, y) of the four reference points were randomly shifted within boundaries of -5 and +5 pixels (Table 1). The corresponding GPS coordinates were translated between -2 and +2 meters around the determined GPS coordinates. Finally, the width and height of the bounding box of a detected cow varied between 0.75 and 1.25 times the original values of the bounding box.

Table 1 Overview of the parameter bounds for the sensitivity analysis of the parameters involved in the localization algorithm.

Parameter	Lower bound	Upper bound
X (pixel)	-5	5
Y (pixel)	-5	5
Latitude (m)	-2	2
Longitude (m)	-2	2
Detection width (%)	0.75	1.25
Detection height (%)	0.75	1.25

From the defined parameter space, 9278 random parameter combinations were sampled to determine the sensitivity of the 18 involved parameters (i.e. x and y coordinates of each reference point and their corresponding longitude and latitude and the height and width of the detection) of the localization algorithm. This analysis was repeated for each location and orientation (Figure 2). This allowed estimating the effect on the parameter sensitivity based on the distance to the camera and the orientation of the cow.

$$S_1 + \dots + S_n + S_{1,2} + \dots + S_{1,2,\dots,n} = 1 \quad (1)$$

$$S_i = \frac{D_i}{\text{var}(Y)} \quad (2)$$

$$S_{i, \text{image}} = S_{i,x} + S_{i,y} + S_{i,xy}; S_{GPS} = S_{i,lat} + S_{i,lon} + S_{i,latlon} \quad (3)$$

With S_i the first-order sensitivity of the i^{th} parameter, $S_{i,j}$ the second-order sensitivity or which considers interaction effects between the i^{th} and j^{th} parameters. S_i is defined as the ratio of the variation in the response caused by changes in the i^{th} parameter, D_i , and the total variation in the response due to changes in all parameters, $\text{var}(Y)$.

The sensitivity of the GPS and image coordinates of the reference points is determined as the sum of the first-order sensitivities of x, y, and latitude and longitude and their respective interactions (Eq. 3).

Results and discussion

Object detection

This research aimed to develop an imaging setup capable of real-time and continuous localization of animals in a pasture. The YoloV8 model achieved promising results, with high mAP50, mAP75, precision, and recall for all model sizes. The precision was consistently high (>0.96) for all model sizes and data splits, i.e. training, validation, and test (Figure 3c). However, in the mAP50, mAP75, and recall a decrease in model performance was observed between the training and test set, suggesting the model might be overfitted. This performance decrease was the smallest for the medium version and the largest for the nano model. Overfitting was caused by collecting images in all splits at a limited number of locations and cows. In addition to cow detection, analysis of videos could also allow identifying cows' behavior (Chen et al., 2021). For outdoor applications in rural areas, it is practically unfeasible to transfer every frame at 30 fps over a mobile network to a server for model inference. This suggests processing all frames on the edge is required, where computing power is limited compared to a server infrastructure. Leading to using smaller models as they require less computing power. For the validation of these smaller models, it is suggested to use independent datasets of grazing cows to provide better insights into potential overfitting.

Figure 3 Evaluation metrics: (a) mAP50 (b) mAP75, (c) Precision, (d) Recall on the training (blue) validation (orange) and test (green) dataset for the nano (n), small (s), and medium (m) yolov8 object detection model.

Localization algorithm

Using the localization algorithm an average positioning error from the GPS references of $0.89 \pm 0.50\text{m}$ (mean \pm one standard deviation) was obtained. The error varied between 0.02m and 2.66m. An ANOVA test indicated that there was no significant effect of the distance to the camera ($p=0.84$) or the orientation of the cow relative to the camera ($p=0.49$) on the positioning error. These results are confirmed by observing Figures 4a and b. However, a Breush-Pagan test indicated that the variation in the prediction error increases significantly ($p=0.001$) with the distance of the cow to the camera. The results are not in line with the findings of Bonneau et al. (2020), who stated that the localization error of the camera-based system increases quadratically with the distance to the camera. This discrepancy might be attributed to the fact that the accuracy assessment in this study was performed using a plastic cow in a pasture, while in the study of Bonneau et al. (2020) the assessment was performed indoors with markers on a perfectly flat floor. The latter approach thus omits the effect of animal detection by an object detection model in the localization. Outdoor camera-based localization was now only validated on flat surfaces, however, this won't be the case in all pastures. To have a better understanding of the general applicability of this approach future research should focus on validation in different types of pastures.

Figure 4 Scatterplot of the localization error (m) in relation to (a) the distance (m) of the cow to the camera and (b) its orientation (°).

Sensitivity analysis

The sensitivity analysis showed that the height of the bounding boxes plays the most important role in determining the accuracy of the proposed localization algorithm, as its relative contribution varies between 7.3% and 77.8% of the total variation of the positioning accuracy (Figure 5). The width of the bounding box and image coordinates of reference points 1, 2, and 4 almost did not influence the localization accuracy. Finally, the image coordinates of the third reference point were also relatively important (Figure 1). From these results, it can be concluded that a very important step in the localization algorithm is the conversion of the cows' bounding box. It is hypothesized that the implementation of animal pose estimation such as Jiang et al. (2022) and Xu et al. (2024) could lead to a more robust conversion and improved localization accuracy. Additionally, future research should also investigate the effect of the different components of the imaging setup such as focal length, height of the camera, and tilt angle.

Figure 5 Sobol sensitivity of the image (im) and GPS (ref) coordinates and width (w) and height (h) of the bounding boxes on the accuracy of the localization algorithm. The boxplots show the distribution in the parameter sensitivity across the locations and orientations.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the nano version YoloV8 object detection model is well suited to detect cows in a pasture, however, the results showed that this model version is more susceptible to overfitting than the medium version. The research confirmed that camera-based localization can be an effective and accurate alternative for GPS collars' outdoor positioning with an average error of 0.89m up to a distance of 100m to the camera. By including pose estimation and behavior identification in the future the accuracy of the presented system for the welfare and monitoring of grazing cattle might be improved.

Acknowledgments

This research was funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe program (Xgain: Grant ID: 101060294). Furthermore, I want to thank Tomma Vlaemynek and Sacha Coussement, and researchers for the ILVO animal department for their assistance in this research.

References

- Arnott, G., Ferris, C. P., & O'connell, N. E. (2017). Review: welfare of dairy cows in continuously housed and pasture-based production systems. *Animal*, *11*(2), 261–273. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1751731116001336>
- Aubé, L., Mialon, M. M., Mollaret, E., Mounier, L., Veissier, I., & de Boyer des Roches, A. (2022). Review: Assessment of dairy cow welfare at pasture: measures available, gaps to address, and pathways to development of ad-hoc protocols. *Animal*, *16*(8), 100597. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ANIMAL.2022.100597>
- Bonneau, M., Vayssade, J. A., Troupe, W., & Arquet, R. (2020). Outdoor animal tracking combining neural network and time-lapse cameras. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, *168*, 105150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.COMPAG.2019.105150>

- Chen, C., Zhu, W., & Norton, T. (2021). Behaviour recognition of pigs and cattle: Journey from computer vision to deep learning. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 187, 106255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.COMPAG.2021.106255>
- Cloet, T. (2022). *Beweiding leeft in Vlaanderen*. https://www.lcvvzw.be/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/E2023_01-Infographic-WeideWijs-samengevoegd.pdf
- Herman, J., & Usher, W. (2017). SALib: An open-source Python library for Sensitivity Analysis. *The Journal of Open Source Software*, 2(9). <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.00097>
- Jiang, L., Lee, C., Teotia, D., & Ostadabbas, S. (2022). Animal pose estimation: A closer look at the state-of-the-art, existing gaps and opportunities. *Computer Vision and Image Understanding*, 222, 103483. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CVIU.2022.103483>
- Jocher, G., Chaurasia, A., & Qiu, J. (2023). *Ultralytics YOLOv8*. <https://github.com/ultralytics/ultralytics>
- JRC. (2015). *Trends in the EU agricultural land within 2015-2030*. <https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2018-12/jrc113717.pdf>
- van den Pol-van Dasselaar, A., Hennessy, D., & Isselstein, J. (2020). Grazing of Dairy Cows in Europe—An In-Depth Analysis Based on the Perception of Grassland Experts. *Sustainability* 2020, Vol. 12, Page 1098, 12(3), 1098. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU12031098>
- Xu, Y., Zhang, J., Zhang, Q., & Tao, D. (2024). ViTPose++: Vision Transformer for Generic Body Pose Estimation. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 46(2), 1212–1230. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.2023.3330016>